

Preparation of 4-Acetylamino-3-Chlorophenyl Stibinate of Sodium.

BY SUDHIR CHANDRA NIYOGY.

The compound to be described in this communication is known in trade as "Von Heyden's 471" but no details as to its method of preparation or properties seem to have been published by Heyden. Recently Brahmachari and Das (*J. of Indian Medical Research*, 13, 17) have prepared this compound by the chlorination of *p*-acetyl-amino-phenyl stibinate of sodium with sodium hypochlorite.

The method of preparation described in this paper is entirely different. (1) The starting material is not acetyl *p*-phenylenediamine but 4-acetylamino-3-chloroaniline. (2) Von Heyden's method (*Fabr. Heyden*, D. R. P. 254421) for the introduction of an antimony complex into the aromatic nucleus is a tedious process and unsatisfactory as regards the yield (which is of the greatest importance in this case). Percy May (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1037) has shown that diazonium chlorides form additive compounds with antimony trichloride solution, which are only very sparingly soluble in ordinary solvents. These when decomposed with sodium hydroxide solution give off the diazo nitrogen and the antimony complex goes into the nucleus.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Acetylamino-3-chloro-aniline (4 g.) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) and water (15 c.c.). This solution was cooled in ice and diazotised. After the diazotisation, hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) was added. Antimony trichloride solution, prepared by dissolving antimony trioxide (4 g.) in hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.), was added slowly to the solution of the diazonium salt with stirring. A crystalline precipitate immediately separated. The whole was then kept in ice for one hour and then filtered at the pump. The precipitate was washed twice with hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.12) to remove antimony trichloride and then with water till free from acid.

The mass was beaten up with water (60 c.c.). Sodium hydroxide

(8 g.) in water (20 c.c.) was added gradually with vigorous stirring. Rapid evolution of nitrogen was noticed and the stirring was continued till it had appreciably slackened, and the whole was allowed to stand overnight. The liquid was then filtered and the residue twice extracted with small quantities of boiling water. The combined filtrate was acidified with dilute sulphuric acid when the free acid separated as a light flocculent precipitate. This was washed thoroughly with water to remove inorganic impurities and then beaten up with a small quantity of water. This emulsion was slightly warmed on the water-bath and sodium hydroxide solution added drop by drop till the whole had gone into solution. The solution was concentrated on the water-bath and absolute alcohol was added in excess when the sodium salt of 4-acetylamino-3-chlorophenyl stibinic acid separated. This was collected, washed with absolute alcohol to remove alkali and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The course of the reaction may be shown thus:

Properties. A light brown amorphous powder, soluble in water, the solution being neutral to litmus. It does not give the diazo reaction. (Found: N, 3.3; Sb, 32.8. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{NClSbNa}$ requires N, 3.8; Sb, 33.3 per cent.).

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DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
& TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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